

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF MANAGEMENT PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract. This article highlights the relevance and problems of management psychology, pedagogical and psychological aspects of child psychology and economic psychology, the influence of an object on relationships, conditions for their optimization, recommendations for ensuring the effectiveness of management activities in general. described in detail.

Key words: management, leader, managerial qualities, leadership leadership.

characteristics, management, activity, professionalism, object, subject, efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

President Sh. As Mirziyoyev noted: “The demand for work It’s one thing to do, it’s quite another to touch people’s personalities. People do not forget that he can obey you in work, but in all other respects he has equal rights with you. ... We all know very well that our people are a noble and honest people. Our people can tolerate everything, but I repeat again and again: they cannot tolerate injustice and injustice. A real leader, a real leader, is appointed not to test people's endurance, but to create suitable conditions for them. Leaders at all levels - be it a minister or a governor, the head of a department or an organization - must be an example and example for everyone with their manners and culture.”

Our grandfather Amir Temur, speaking about his leadership qualities, said the following: “I conquered people with openness and compassion. I strove for justice and strove to be away from oppression“Truly, leadership and its correct implementation is an art, a skill. Because this is a multifaceted and complex

process. For this reason, its study and research began in ancient times and continues to this day. How many theories and doctrines have been created and are being created on this matter.

The modern theory of the art of leadership appeared in the United States. The first literature in this area was published in European countries, where the old management system began to lose its importance.

If you pay attention to modern management, then all that remains is to list the devices and equipment in the office as the most reliable and obedient control object in a modern organization. Employees, understood as objects of direct management, have become a “potential” element of a complex management process. Interacting with this “element”, constantly pushing it towards the goal, in a word, the effectiveness of today’s management largely depends on the psychological preparation of the leader. The scope of research on management improvement is so broad that at first glance it seems that it is focused on only one topic, but its diversity leads to the emergence of conflicting ideas in management science. Continuation of the idea that management has a specific aspect allows us to define the subject area of psychology, in particular, the psychology of management. Based on a series of analyses, we come to the conclusion that psychological phenomena in management can be divided into three main groups:

- The subject of management is the leader.
- The object of control is the employee.
- The relationship between the subject and the object of management.

This grouping of psychological phenomena related to management is arbitrary, and the study of each of them inevitably includes the other two. In particular, since the leader as a subject of management becomes the main subject of many studies, each of his actions implies an employee and, naturally, is interpreted within the framework of certain relationships. Even the activities of a leader to improve his personality are defined as an internal psychological attitude,

an attitude towards himself. This limitation of the subject of management, on the one hand, allows us to define our subject for the science of psychology, and on the other hand, is expressed in the formation of completely new views on the science of management. In particular, it would not be an exaggeration to say that the ideas and thoughts proposed by proponents of the phenomenological approach to management and leadership activity, in fact, were able to express not only the area and direction of research, but also the “point” of psychology. The introduction of such technical tools into the life of a modern manager gives new meaning to the issue of technological improvement of managerial professionalism. In our opinion, the issue of professionalizing management and increasing the professionalism of managers, like any other area, can only be resolved on the basis of the integration and activities of various scientific areas. We cannot deny that the concept of management psychology exists not only in organizations and enterprises, but also in a number of activity processes discussed above. It can be seen that the concept of management psychology is present not only in the activities of the manager and employees, on the contrary, this concept is present in many types of activities. It is necessary to study management by connecting it with the economic basis of society, taking into account two organizational, technical and socio-economic aspects of management. Organizational and technical management of net consumption division of labor and cooperation in preparing products to achieve value different Socio-economic management of existing production is related to relationships and defines management goals. Organizational Technical management is a type of activity that allows you to create conditions for increasing labor productivity and production efficiency.

The purpose of socio-economic management is to ensure effective work of employees.

is to create conditions for them, form a reliable national system of their social protection, ensure employment and support low-income segments of the

population. The final result of the reforms being implemented today in our country largely depends on leaders and their professional skills in management. In this regard, first of all, it is necessary to pay special attention to developing the skills of management personnel and civil servants to work with civil society institutions and people.

Such abilities and skills can only be developed through special educational activities.

possible In this regard, today the development of scientific research in the field of management and the training of management personnel is a very important issue.

We are waiting for its result. Actions aimed at specific results in this area pose pressing challenges for pedagogical and psychological science. For example, the need to select suitable candidates, to fairly assess their managerial potential and abilities when appointing management personnel to positions in various areas of management has always been an urgent problem. It will not remain the same. It is necessary to integrate the characteristics and qualities of a person, his experience, existing knowledge, skills and abilities into the professional and personal qualities characteristic of modern leaders.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we note that the problem of management is widely studied in the field of psychology on the basis of various theories, concepts, approaches, positions, directions. At the same time, it is important for the higher education system that the manager and the leader are expressed in one person, and the official leader must organize the management process, maximally combining the goals of the organization with the interests of employees. possible. It is this factor, especially high qualifications in the field of profession, that serves as the basis for a leader's rise to the leadership level. Separately, it should be noted that management psychology is recognized as a new, modern and researched direction

within the branches of psychology. By introducing theoretical and practical aspects of management psychology into the life of society, it will be possible to avoid various conflict situations that may arise between teams and workers, and production will continue to grow both quantitatively and qualitatively.

Recommendations

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